

Definition of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGV)

Contribution of Geodesy to Earth Observation

White Paper by
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Foreword

A cornerstone in the implementation of the GGOS Strategic Plan 2024-2034 is the definition of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs) to highlight the contribution of geodesy to Earth system monitoring. Essential Variables (EVs) are specific measurements, observations or parameters that are critical for understanding, monitoring and predicting changes in complex systems such as the Earth's climate, environment or socio-economic conditions. These variables are selected on the basis of their significant impact on these systems, their ability to provide actionable information and their usefulness in supporting scientific research, decision-making and policy development. In this context, the concept of variables does not adhere to the same definition as in physics or mathematics, but rather to the principle of being fit for purpose.

The Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) was the first community to introduce the concept of EVs, the Essential Climate Variables (ECVs), which have been widely adopted by the scientific and policy communities. Subsequently, the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) defined a complementary set of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) with standards aligned with the ECVs. Similarly, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), a partner of the Biodiversity Observing Network of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO BON), has initiated the definition of Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs). Under the GEO program *GEOEssential*, there are currently other ongoing initiatives to introduce additional sets of EVs, not only to describe the Earth System, but also the socio-economic system, including for example urban development, transport and infrastructure, energy and minerals, health, agriculture, etc.

Following the same arrangement of GCOS and GOOS, which defined the ECVs and EOVs, respectively, the Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS) of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG) is working on the definition of the essential geodetic variables. This document describes the first concept for the definition of EGVs. This concept

considers 21 EGVs based on 59 geodetic products. The products represent measurable parameters, processed/value-added datasets, quantities, and models as well as the infrastructure and the standards needed as foundation for the EGVs. As the different observing systems GGOS, GCOS and GOOS observe components of the same Earth, there are some essential variables that are common to all three. In such cases, geodesy makes a significant contribution to the characterization of these variables and complements or underpins the products provided by the other observing systems. Another set of essential variables are of a purely geodetic nature and are therefore defined for the first time in this document.

To clearly define essential variables, it is important to first understand the terms *essential* and *variable*. *Essential* means something that is absolutely necessary, indispensable, or fundamental to the core of a concept. A *variable* is considered essential if it significantly enhances the reliability and accuracy of desired outcomes. It may also be deemed essential if it provides critical insights relevant to a specific objective, even if it is not directly measurable or related to a physical/mathematical characteristic. The *essentiality* of a variable may vary according to the needs of different communities or audiences, such as those in the scientific or policy-making communities. Any variable may be considered essential by someone or for the achievement of a particular goal, making the definition of essential variables inherently subjective. Developing these definitions requires a structured process that balances collective interests and ideally secures international recognition. To this end, it is imperative to circulate this document widely and gather feedback from the geodetic community as a whole. The first step in this process is to establish a consensus on a catalogue of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs) and their supporting products. Once broad agreement is reached, the next phase will involve the characterization of the geodetic products that support the EGVs. This effort will also include identifying responsible stewards for each EGV.

Community participation is being encouraged through review by or consultation with the GGOS Science Panel, the GGOS Governing Board, the IAG Executive Committee composed of representatives of its key components (Services, Commissions, Inter-Commission Committees, Projects), and the members of the United Nations Global Geodetic Center of Excellence (UN-GGCE). Having incorporated their feedback, this document presents the first catalogue of EGVs and establishes the basis for the next steps in their characterization, maintenance, and long-term sustainability.

Document History

V	Date	Changes
1.0	02-02-2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Initial version.
2.0	19-02-2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Minor update of chapters 1 to 3.2.▪ Chapter 3.3 added.
3.0	08-04-2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Minor update of all chapters with inclusion of some new geodetic products.▪ Version given to the GGOS Science Panel for review.
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6.0	08-01-2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Update including feedback from the GGOS Governing Board Members.▪ References (footnotes) added.▪ EGV icons added.▪ Version given to the Executive Committee and key components of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG) for review.
7.0	15-01-2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Update including feedback from the IAG Executive Committee and from the UN Global Geodetic Center of Excellence (UN-GGCE).▪ EGVs of Level 0 and Level 1 added.▪ Level 0 renamed as Basis.▪ Classification of the EGVs in different levels illustrated through two examples: Determination of the ITRF and modelling of the gravity field.▪ Definition of the domain and sub-domain for the EGVs described in more detail.▪ Relevance statement for each EGV added.▪ Next steps described in “<i>The Way Forward</i>”.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to define the essential variables provided by geodesy, which are capable of describing and monitoring the Earth in a systematic and a sustainable way. Geodesy observes the Earth as a whole, from the interior to the surface, including the atmosphere, with regional and local refinements, and provides a large number of products for this purpose. Moreover, geodetic products, infrastructure and standards are needed for all ground and space bound positioning, navigation and timing tasks, and thus play a fundamental role in modern society¹. So far, however, these products suffer from a lack of visibility for the global society (non-geodetic communities, administration, decision makers, science and others) and in some cases they are also not easy to understand for non-experts. In addition, geodesy as a discipline is also not well known to the public and therefore, there is a need to better promote these geodetic products^{2,3}.

For these reasons, a set of essential geodetic variables shall be identified and requirements for them shall be specified. In order to clearly state that such geodetic variables monitor or observe the Earth system it is proposed to name these variables as:

Essential Geodetic Variables:
Contribution of Geodesy to Earth Observation
with the acronym
EGV

¹ More details on the contribution of Geodesy to science and society may be found in Plag, H. P.; Pearlman M. (Eds.) (2009): *Global Geodetic Observing System: Meeting the Requirements of a Global Society on a Changing Planet in 2020*, Springer Verlag, https://doi.org/10.1007/9783642026874_3.

² GGOS, the Global Geodetic Observing System of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG), envisions a future where geodetic data and products are not a scientific asset only, but an essential resource guiding decision-making across diverse fields, see Sánchez, L.; Miyahara, B.; Craddock, A.; Sehna, M.; Angermann, D.; Gross, R.; Schuh, H. (2024b): GGOS Strategic Plan 2024-2034. GGOS Coordinating Office, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10571157>.

³ The United Nations, through its Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence (UN-GGCE), recognises the significant vulnerabilities in the global geodetic supply chain and calls for action to ensure long-term and reliable geodetic products, see UN-GGCE (2024): *Hidden Risk: How weaknesses in the global geodesy supply chain could have catastrophic impacts on critical infrastructure and national economies. Background report for decision-makers*, Version 1.1, https://ggim.un.org/UNGGCE/documents/20240620-Hidden_Risk_Report.pdf.

An EGV is an observation or parameter that critically contributes to the characterization of the geometric and physical shape of the Earth and to its orientation in space.

EGVs shall be defined by GGOS (Global Geodetic Observing System⁴), which is a component of the IAG (International Association of Geodesy)⁵. This is a similar arrangement to that used for the definition of ECVs (Essential Climate Variables^{6,7}), which were defined in 2011 by GCOS (Global Climate Observing System⁸), and for the definition of EOVs (Essential Ocean Variables^{9,10}), which were defined in 2014 by GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System¹¹). All essential variables shall be continuously monitored and the products supporting them shall meet specific requirements in terms of spatial and temporal resolution, accuracy, latency and consistency^{12,13}. Since the different observing systems GGOS, GCOS and GOOS observe components of the same Earth, there are essential variables that are common to all three¹⁴. In such cases, geodetic products provide significant additional contributions to characterize these variables and complement the products from other organizations. Another set of essential variables is of purely geodetic nature and therefore, they are newly defined by GGOS.

The subsequent chapters define the criteria to declare a variable as essential and identify levels of EGVs (chapter 2). Further, a first classification is provided for EGVs identifying the domain, subdomain, scientific area, relevance and the related geodetic products (chapter 3).

⁴ <https://geodesy.science/ggos/>

⁵ Main characteristics and on-going activities of GGOS are summarised in Sánchez L., Riddell A., Angermann D., Rodríguez J., Sehnal M., Gruber T., Gross R., Lidberg M., Craddock A., Ferrándiz J.M. (2024). *The Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS) – Harnessing Geodesy for the Benefit of Science and Society*, *allgemeine vermessungsnachrichten*, 06-06/2024: 256-269, <https://doi.org/10.14627/avn.2024.5-6.4>.

⁶ <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables>

⁷ Bojinski, S.; Verstraete, M.; Peterson, T.C.; Richter, C.; Simmons, A.; Zemp, M. (2014): *The Concept of Essential Climate Variables in Support of Climate Research, Applications, and Policy*, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 95: 1431–1443, <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-13-00047.1>.

⁸ <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/home>

⁹ <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>

¹⁰ Fischer, A.; Grimes, S. (2012): *Definition of Ecosystem Essential Ocean Variables*. Technical Report, GEOWOWWP6-IOU-I6.1.1, GEOS Interoperability for Weather, Ocean and Water, IOC-UNESCO, 24 pp.

¹¹ <https://goosocean.org/>

¹² Bombelli A., Serral I., Blonda P., Masó J., Plag H.-P., Jules-Plag S., McCallum I. (2015), *EVs current status in different communities and way to move forward*, *ConnectinGEO*, https://ddd.uab.cat/pub/worpaper/2015/146882/D2_2_EVs_current_status_in_different_communities_and_way_to_move_forward.pdf.

¹³ Patias, P., Verde, N., Mallinis, G., Georgiadis, C., Giuliani, G., Serral, I., McCallum, I., Kussul, N., Lehmann, A., Masó, J. (2018), *Best practice white paper on use of EVs for UN programs*. GEOEssential Deliverable 8.1, https://www.geoessential.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/D8.1_v5.pdf.

¹⁴ There are currently other ongoing initiatives to introduce additional sets of EVs, not only to describe the Earth system, but also the socio-economic system, including for example biodiversity, urban development, energy and minerals, health, agriculture, etc., see e.g. Lehmann, A.; Mazzetti, P.; Santoro, M.; Nativi, S.; Masó, J.; Serral, I.; Spengler, D.; Niamir, A.; Lacroix, P.; Ambrosone, M.; McCallum, I.; Kussul, N.; Patias, P.; Rodila, D.; Ray, N.; Giuliani, G. (2022): *Essential Earth Observation variables for high-level multi-scale indicators and policies*, *Environmental Science & Policy*, vol 131, 105-117, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.12.024>.

2. Definition and Criteria of EGVs

EGVs are crucial to characterize the geodetic properties of the Earth and are needed to understand the dynamics of the Earth system in all its components and their interplay. They are essential to continuously monitor the Earth system, to assess possible risks, to develop mitigation strategies and to underpin the availability of sustainable geodetic services. They are required to support the work of the UN-GGCE (United Nations Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence^{15,16}) and other high level international organizations like the UN-FCCC (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change¹⁷), the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change¹⁸), the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS¹⁹) and GEO (Group on Earth Observations²⁰) together with its Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS²¹), GEOEssential Program²² and Knowledge Hub²³. The definition of EGVs is indeed one of the main activities set out in the First Joint Development Plan for Global Geodesy²⁴ designed by the UN-GGCE.

EGVs comprise physical and geometric variables, as well as *fit-for-purpose* variables needed for continuous, consistent and reliable geodetic monitoring of the Earth. These fit-for-purpose variables include observing infrastructure and standards and conventions, for instance. EGVs shall be identified based on the following main criteria, which are

¹⁵ <https://ggim.un.org/UNGGCE/>

¹⁶ United Nations Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence, Strategy and Operating Plan, V.1.0, https://ggim.un.org/UNGGCE/documents/UN_GGCE_Strategy_%20and_Operating_Plan_v1.0.pdf

¹⁷ <https://unfccc.int/>

¹⁸ <https://www.ipcc.ch/>

¹⁹ <https://ceos.org/>

²⁰ <https://earthobservations.org/>

²¹ <https://old.earthobservations.org/geoss.php>

²² <https://www.geoessential.eu/>

²³ <https://gkhub.earthobservations.org/>

²⁴ 1st Joint Development Plan for Global Geodesy, United Nations Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence, Bonn, Germany, https://ggim.un.org/UNGGCE/documents/Version_1.0_1st_Joint_Development_Plan_for_Global_Geodesy_EN.pdf.

adapted from criteria for the definition of ECVs⁷, and extended by two additional criteria specifically applicable to geodetic products (sustainability and consistency/interoperability).

Relevance: The variable is critical for characterizing the geometric and physical properties of the system Earth and its temporal changes.

Feasibility: Observing or deriving the variable on a global scale is technically feasible using proven and scientifically understood methods.

Cost effectiveness: Generating and archiving data about the variable is affordable, mainly relying on coordinated observing systems using proven technology, taking advantage of historical datasets (when possible).

Sustainability: The variable shall be made available over decades and the tools for observing it shall be sustainable.

Consistency and interoperability: The variables shall be consistent in terms of reference systems and standards/conventions, so that they can be easily combined or used together and are interoperable.

Sustainability requires availability of observation systems providing all observables needed for an EGV continuously over decades and with similar quality. To achieve this, the geodetic infrastructure providing the observables has to be operated and further developed continuously. **Consistency** is a major requirement for EGVs and the underlying geodetic products. All products defining an EGV shall be processed based on agreed standards and conventions in order to ensure interoperability. Processing centres shall follow specific conventions released or adopted by the IAG^{25,26,27,28} and the recommendations provided by the GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards^{29,30}. Therefore, geodetic observing infrastructure and geodetic standards and conventions are considered as the basis level for the EGVs in this concept. Further levels of EGVs are defined, mainly representing the level of detail or complexity of a variable. Following the conventions usually applied to Earth Observation satellite data^{31,32}, the lowest level represents the observed data (i.e. measurements), while the highest level is defined by combined products providing relevant geodetic and Earth system parameters.

²⁵ Petit, G., Luzum, B. Eds. (2010): *IERS Conventions (2010)*. IERS Technical Note No. 36. Verlag des Bundesamtes für Kartographie und Geodäsie, Frankfurt a. M., <https://www.iers.org/IERS/EN/Publications/TechnicalNotes/tn36.html>.

²⁶ Sánchez, L., Ågren, J., Huang, J., Wang, Y.M., Mäkinen, J., Pail, R., Barzaghi, R., Vergos, G.S., Ahlgren, K., Liu, Q. (2021): *Strategy for the realisation of the International Height Reference System (IIRS)*, *J Geod*, 95, 3, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-021-01481-0>.

²⁷ Wziontek, H., Bonvalot, S., Falk, R., Gabalda, G., Mäkinen, J., Pálinkáš, V., Rülke, A., Vitushkin, L. (2021): *Status of the International Gravity Reference System and Frame*. *J Geod* 95, 7, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-020-01438-9>.

²⁸ Hohenkerk, C. (2011), *Standards of Fundamental Astronomy*. *Scholarpedia*, 6(1):11404, http://www.scholarpedia.org/article/Standards_of_Fundamental_Astronomy.

²⁹ Angermann D., Gruber T., Gerstl M., Heinkelmann R., Hugentobler U., Sánchez L., Steigenberger P. (2016), *GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards: Inventory of standards and conventions used for the generation of IAG products*. In: Drewes H., Kuglitsch F., Adám J., Rózsa S. (Eds.), *The Geodesists' Handbook 2016*, *Journal of Geodesy*, 90(10), 1095-1156, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-016-0948-z>.

³⁰ Angermann D., Gruber T., Gerstl M., Heinkelmann R., Hugentobler U., Sánchez L., Steigenberger P. (2020), *Bureau of Products and Standards: Inventory of standards and conventions used for the generation of IAG products*. In: Poutanen M., Rózsa S. (Eds.), *The Geodesists' Handbook 2020*, *Journal of Geodesy*, 94(11), 221–292, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-020-01434-z>.

³¹ <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn/earth-observation-data-basics/data-processing-levels>

³² <https://help.marine.copernicus.eu/en/articles/5046705-which-levels-are-used-for-data-processing>

The levels of EGVs are coherent with the process of modelling changes in the Earth system from geodetic measurements (see Fig. 1³³).

Fig. 1: From geodetic measurements to Earth system modelling³³

In this context, the following scheme for EGV levels is proposed:

- Basis:** Geodetic observing infrastructure and standards/conventions required to produce higher level EGVs.
- Level 1:** Data collected by satellites, airborne or ground-based infrastructure annotated with geo-location and epoch. They are based on agreed standards and conventions.
- Level 2:** Products determined from a combination of various Earth Observation data sets describing specific parameters of the Earth system in the space and time domains.
- Level 3:** High-level accumulated products describing the geometric and physical shape of the Earth or its orientation in space as well as further parameters of the Earth system, after performing a significant data processing and/or data combination. These variables are application-oriented and shall be directly applicable to multidisciplinary Earth system monitoring.

Space- and ground-based geodetic infrastructure is considered as a basis as it is necessary to assess the availability and quality of the observing infrastructure in order to plan improvements and further development. The standards and conventions are also a basis of the EGVs as they are essential for the analysis of geodetic data and for the generation of consistent geodetic products. EGVs at Level 3 are relevant to a large user community and need to be understandable to non-experts. Level 1 and Level 2 variables are more specific and require more expert knowledge to be used. These EGVs are

³³ Sánchez L., Riddell A., Angermann D., Rodríguez J., Sehnal M., Gruber T., Gross R., Lidberg M., Craddock A., Ferrándiz J.M. (2024). The Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS) – Harnessing Geodesy for the Benefit of Science and Society, *allgemeine vermessungsnachrichten*, 06-06/2024: 256-269, <https://doi.org/10.14627/avn.2024.5-6.4>.

considered to be more relevant for the geodetic community but are required for the determination of Level 3 EGVs.

Figure 2 shows as an example the relation between EGVs of different levels and some related products for the determination of the EGVs “Global Reference Frames” (in this case the ITRF, *International Terrestrial Reference Frame*) and “Earth Orientation Parameters” (EOP). The EGV “Geodetic Infrastructure”, which comprises the station networks of VLBI (*Very Long Baseline Interferometry*), SLR (*Satellite Laser Ranging*), GNSS (*Global Navigation Satellite Systems*) and DORIS (*Doppler Orbitography and Radiopositioning Integrated by Satellite*) as well as the respective space segments (quasars for VLBI and satellites for the three other space geodetic techniques), together with the EGV “Standards and Conventions”, form the foundation (Basis) for generating the EGV “Geodetic Observations” (Level 1). These observations provide the backbone for the computation of the EGV “Station Positions and Variations” (Level 2) and are combined into the high-level EGVs “Global Reference Frames” (in this case the ITRF) and “Earth Orientation Parameters” (Level 3). Along this processing chain, various by-products related to the Earth system such as total electron content (TEC), zenith path delays (ZPD), plate kinematics or deformation models can also be calculated and then combined to derive high-level EGVs, i.e., “Atmosphere Parameters” and “Land Geometry” (Level 3).

Fig. 2: Relation between essential geodetic variables of different levels and some related products for the ITRF and EOP determination. Coloured circles represent EGVs (orange states for global domain, green for land domain), grey circles represent products

Similarly, Fig. 3 shows the relationship between essential geodetic variables and various products related to gravity field modelling and reference frames in physical geodesy. The EGVs “Geodetic Infrastructure” and “Geodetic Standards and Conventions” form the basis once again. The EGV “Geodetic Observations” (Level 1) includes geometric observations (in this case, *low-low satellite-to-satellite tracking*) and physical observations (in this case, *satellite gravity gradiometry, gravimetry, and clock frequencies*). These observations form the basis for computing the Level 2 EGVs “Satellite Orbits” and “Land and Marine Gravity Data”. These in turn are the basis for the Level 3 EGVs related to gravity field modelling and reference frames for gravimetry and physical heights in global and regional domains, namely: “Global Earth Gravity Field” (with the products *Global Gravity Field Models, Topography Gravity Field Models, and Gravity Field Quantities*), “Global Reference Frames” (in this case *Gravity Reference Frame and Height Reference Frame*), “Regional Gravity Field Model” (with the products *Regional Geoid Model and Regional Gravity Field Quantities*) and “Regional Reference Frames” (including *Regional Gravity Reference Frame, Regional Height Reference Frame, and Vertical Datum Parameters*).

Fig. 3: Relation between essential geodetic variables of different levels and some products related to gravity field modelling and reference frames in physical geodesy. Coloured circles represent EGVs (orange states for global domain, violet for land and/or ocean domain), grey circles represent products.

3. Classification of EGVs

The classification of EGVs defines for each variable the *domain*, the *subdomain*, the *scientific area*, a person or organization who takes care about the variable, i.e., the *steward* (to be identified in a later stage) and the related *geodetic products* contributing to the EGV. The domain is defined as *Global*, *Land* and *Ocean*, while the subdomain specifies whether the variable relates to the *Geometry* or *Physics* of the Earth. The domain *Global* covers variables that refer to the entire Earth in all its components, such as *Earth Orientation Parameters*, *Global Reference Frames*, *Satellite Orbits*, *Global Earth Gravity Field*, *Atmosphere Parameters*, etc. The *Land* and *Ocean* domains refer to EGVs that are primarily relevant to terrestrial or marine environments, respectively. For instance, *Land Geometry* and *Inland Water Level* only occur in land areas. Similarly, *Sea Level* or *Sea Ice* only occur in ocean areas. Other variables may have the domain *Land/Ocean*, when they occur in coastal areas. Table 1 shows the list of proposed EGVs and their classification according to the level, domain, and subdomain. Table 2 identifies the main geodetic products associated with the definition of the EGVs. Section 3.5 provides an overview about the specific geodetic products contributing to the EGVs.

As shown in Table 1, a total of eight EGVs correspond to ECVs of GCOS and two EGVs correspond to EOVs of GOOS. It should be noted that the definition of these EGVs and the associated products does not fully match with the definition of ECVs and EOVs. The reason for this is that the concept of the EGV definition focuses primarily on the available geodetic data and products. Thus, the geodetic products considered in the EGVs provide additional information for the essential variables defined by GCOS and GOOS.

Table 1: List of proposed EGVs

EGV	Level	Domain	Subdomain	ECV*	EOV**
Earth Orientation Parameters	L3	Global	Geometric		
Global Reference Frames	L3	Global	Geometric/Physical		
Global Earth Gravity Field	L3	Global	Physical		
Regional Reference Frames	L3	Land/ Ocean***	Geometric/Physical		
Regional Gravity Field Model	L3	Land/ Ocean***	Physical		
Land Geometry	L3	Land	Geometric		
Sea Surface	L3	Ocean	Geometric	X	X
Sea Level	L3	Ocean	Physical	X	
Sea Ice	L3	Ocean	Geometric	X	X
Ice Sheets	L3	Land	Geometric/Physical	X	
Glaciers	L3	Land	Geometric/Physical	X	
Inland Water Level	L3	Land	Geometric/Physical	X	
Terrestrial Water Storage	L3	Land	Physical	X	
Atmosphere Parameters	L3	Global	Physical	X	
Satellite Orbits	L2	Global	Geometric		

	Station Positions and Variations	L2	Global	Geometric		
	Sea Water Level Records	L2	Ocean	Geometric		
	Land and Marine Gravity Data	L2	Land/ Ocean ***	Physical		
	Geodetic Observations	L1	Global	Geometric/Physical		
	Geodetic Standards and Conventions	Basis	Global	Geometric/Physical		
	Geodetic Infrastructure	Basis	Global	Geometric/Physical		

* Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs) common to Essential Climate Variables (ECVs)

** Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs) common to Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)

*** For regional applications at land and ocean

Table 2: Geodetic products associated with the definition of an EGV

Acronym	Definition	Acronym	Definition
AGD	Absolute Gravity Data	MGC	Mean Geostrophic Currents
CBM	Conventional Background Models	MGD	Marine Gravity Data
CPO	Celestial Pole Offset	MRWL	Mean Regional Water Level
CRF	Celestial Reference Frame	MSL	(Global) Mean Sea Level
DEM	Digital Elevation Model	MSS	Mean Sea Surface
DOT	Dynamic Ocean Topography	NSG	Numerical Standards in Geodesy
DTM	Digital Terrain Model	PKM	Plate Kinematic Model
EOT	Empirical Ocean Tide Model	PM	Polar Motion
ESD	Earth Surface Deformation	RGFQ	Regional Gravity Field Quantities
ESO	Earth Observation Satellite Orbits	RGM	Regional Geoid Model
GFQ	Gravity Field Quantities	RGRF	Regional Gravity Reference Frame
GFV	Glacier Flow Velocities	RHRF	Regional Height Reference Frame
GGM	Global Gravity Field Models	RMSL	Relative Mean Sea Level
GGO	Geodetic Geometric Observations	RSLC	Relative Sea Level Change
GIM	Global Ionosphere Maps	RTRF	Regional Terrestrial Reference Frame
GIT	Glacier Ice Thickness	RWLC	Regional Water Level Change
GMC	Glacier Mass Change	SES	Sea State
GOCB	GNSS Satellite Orbits, Clocks, Biases	SIE	Sea Ice Extension
GPO	Geodetic Physical Observations	SIV	Sea Ice Volume
GRF	Gravity Reference Frame	SLA	Sea Level Anomaly
GSI	Geodetic Space Infrastructure	SLC	(Global) Sea Level Change
GTI	Geodetic Terrestrial Infrastructure	SPTS	Station Position Time Series
HRF	Height Reference Frame	SWLR	Sea Water Level Records
IMC	Ice Mass Change	TDM	Thermosphere Density Model
IST	Ice Sheet Thickness	TGD	Time Series Gravity Data
IWV	Integrated Water Vapor	TGFM	Topographic Gravity Field Models
LGD	Land Gravity Data	TRF	Terrestrial Reference Frame
LOD	Length of Day	TWSA	Terrestrial Water Storage Anomaly
MDT	Mean Dynamic Topography	UT1	Universal Time
		VDP	Vertical Datum Parameter

3.1 Level 3 EGVs

	<h2 style="text-align: center;">Earth Orientation Parameters</h2>
Domain	Global
Subdomain	Geometric
Scientific Area	Change of the orientation of the Earth with respect to a global reference frame (celestial pole offsets, UT1, LOD, polar motion).
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Celestial Pole Offset (CPO): <i>Differences with respect to the conventional celestial pole position defined by precession and nutation models with respect to the CRF.</i> ▪ Universal Time (UT1): <i>Computed from a measure of the Earth's angle with respect to the CRF, called the Earth Rotation Angle.</i> ▪ Length of Day (LOD): <i>Time series of LOD variations.</i> ▪ Polar Motion (PM): <i>Time series of pole coordinates relative to the TRF and rates of PM.</i>
Relevance	<p>Earth Orientation Parameters (EOPs) describe irregularities in the Earth's rotation and orientation in space. They are essential for connecting the terrestrial reference frame with the celestial reference. EOPs are required for satellite-based services such as Earth Observation, communication, positioning, navigation and timing on the Earth's surface, as well as for orientating astronomical instruments. They are also essential for planning space mission launches, docking operations and trajectories, and for communicating with devices exploring deep space. Furthermore, EOP time series are a key source of information for Earth system research, as they reveal a multitude of time-variable effects produced by the interaction of gravitational and geodynamic processes within and between Earth system components.</p>

	<h2 style="text-align: center;">Global Reference Frames</h2>
Domain	Global
Subdomain	Geometric/Physical
Scientific Area	Geometric reference frames for the determination of the positions of astronomical objects in the celestial system and of points on or above the Earth surface in the terrestrial system. Physical reference frames

	for determining the gravity acceleration and the equipotential surface as a height reference.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Celestial Reference Frame (CRF): <i>Catalog of precise equatorial coordinates of extragalactic radio sources.</i> ▪ Terrestrial Reference Frame (TRF): <i>Concrete points (markers) attached to the solid Earth crust with precisely determined coordinates (mean 3D positions of the stations and their motions).</i> ▪ Gravity Reference Frame (GRF): <i>Absolute gravity measurements traceable to the International System of Units (SI) that contain conventional temporal gravity corrections.</i> ▪ Height Reference Frame (HRF): <i>Reference stations homogeneously distributed over the world and with known geopotential numbers or height values with respect to a global common reference surface.</i>
Relevance	<p>Global reference frames are essential for describing the position and motion of the Earth and other celestial bodies (including artificial satellites), for assigning time-dependent coordinates to points, observing instruments or objects on or near the Earth’s surface, and for modelling the stationary and time-variable components of the Earth’s gravity field. Geometric reference frames (TRF, CRF) are essential for satellite-based Earth Observation, navigation, positioning and timing, and for detecting changes in the Earth's shape, surface kinematics (solid Earth, ice, water), and rotation. Physical reference frames (GRF, HRF) are essential for determining heights above mean sea level and for detecting changes governed by the gravity field, particularly those caused by mass transport within the Earth system. Global reference frames form the backbone of all applications based on the determination, management and use of georeferenced data (also called geospatial or geodata), such as land administration, engineering, positioning, navigation, timing, geo-information systems, telecommunications, etc. They also provide the basis for quantifying the effects of Earth system processes, such as plate tectonics, sea level change, post-glacial rebound, climate change, earthquakes and volcanic activity, etc., as well as for operating early warning systems to protect against natural hazards.</p>

	<h2>Global Earth Gravity Field</h2>
Domain	Global
Subdomain	Physical

Scientific Area	Global Earth gravity field in the spectral and spatial domains including derived quantities with respect to a reference (ellipsoidal) gravity field.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Global Gravity Field Models (GGM): <i>Spherical or ellipsoidal harmonic series of gravity potential either as mean or as a temporal series (low degree harmonics from satellite-only combined models).</i> ▪ Topographic Gravity Field Models (TGFM): <i>Spherical or ellipsoidal harmonic series of gravity potential originated by the attraction of the Earth's topographic masses.</i> ▪ Gravity Field Quantities (GFQ): <i>Calculated gravity functionals on grids or selected points either with reference to an ellipsoidal reference field (height anomaly, geoid, gravity disturbance, gravity anomaly, deflections of the vertical, equivalent water height) or as full signal (gravitation, gravitational potential, gravity, gravity potential, normal gravity, normal potential, gravity gradient).</i>
Relevance	The Earth's gravity field and its variations are closely related to mass distribution and mass transport within the Earth. Precise knowledge of the global gravity field (observed by satellites) is essential for modelling geodynamic processes in the ocean and solid Earth, revealing mass redistribution within the Earth system, computing the global geoid (the reference surface for physical heights) and determining precise satellite orbits, especially for positioning and navigation satellites, low Earth orbiters, and Earth Observation missions. The global geoid is essential for studying sea level changes, modelling ocean circulation, and monitoring the state of the hydrosphere, including water storage, ice mass balance and the global water cycle. Globally observed gravity field quantities are essential for detecting mass density anomalies in the Earth's crust and mantle to study the Earth's interior dynamics, as well as for revealing major tectonic structures and subsurface processes.

	<h2>Regional Reference Frames</h2>
Domain	Land/Ocean
Subdomain	Geometric/Physical
Scientific Area	Regional densification of global reference frames to improve the station distribution and provide access to the global TRF, GRF and HRF at regional/national scales. A regional height system is not necessarily a regional densification of the HRF, as the reference surface of most of the existing physical height systems is linked to the mean sea level

	determined at a tide gauge and consequently to the regional geoid model (RGM). The link between the regional height systems and the global HRF is provided by vertical datum parameters (VDP).
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regional Terrestrial Reference Frame (RTRF): <i>Concrete points (markers) attached to the solid Earth crust with precisely determined coordinates (mean 3D positions of the stations and their motions) for regional networks.</i> ▪ Regional Gravity Reference Frame (RGRF): <i>Absolute gravity measurements traceable to the SI that contain conventional temporal gravity corrections.</i> ▪ Regional Height Reference Frame (RHRF): <i>Reference stations regionally distributed with known geopotential numbers or height values with respect to the global HRF reference surface.</i> ▪ Vertical Datum Parameter (VDP): <i>Connection of the regional height system to the global height reference frame (HRF).</i>
Relevance	Regional reference frames are essential for accessing global geodetic reference frames at regional/national scales, ensuring compatibility with international standards, and enabling the same accuracy and stability as the global frames. As regional reference frames are characterized by denser station distribution than the global frames, they are essential for improving regional GNSS and remote sensing data analysis and for detecting small-scale tectonic activity, ground deformation, natural risks, and other regional effects. They also provide the basis for national coordinate systems, cadastral surveying, land administration/management, infrastructure deployment, and sustainable development. They are also essential for improving positioning and navigation accuracy for local users (e.g. real-time-based applications, surveyors, engineers, GNSS users, and in general, any geospatial application).

	<h2>Regional Gravity Field Model</h2>
Domain	Land/Ocean
Subdomain	Physical
Scientific Area	Regional gravity field models representing gravity field quantities with high resolution. These models are determined from a combination of satellite gravimetry with ground, airborne and marine gravity data providing the highest possible spatial resolution.
EGV Stewards	tbd

Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regional Geoid Model (RGM): <i>Grid of regional geoid estimates describing the geopotential surface serving as the height reference surface for a country or a specific region.</i> ▪ Regional Gravity Field Quantities (RGFQ): <i>Point values or grids of regional gravity anomalies, gravity disturbances, deflection of the vertical.</i>
Relevance	<p>Regional gravity field modelling is essential for increasing the resolution and accuracy of global gravity models on regional and national scales, as it captures small-scale gravity features that are averaged out in global models. In particular, local geoid models are essential for establishing/maintaining national and regional physical height reference systems for infrastructure planning and for converting GNSS heights to physical heights. Observed regional gravity field quantities are essential for detecting subsurface mass density anomalies, which are useful for exploring minerals, oil and gas or geothermal energy. They also support geological mapping and basement structure analysis, and studies of regional crustal structure, tectonic uplift/subsidence, and volcanic activity. Moreover, they are useful for improving modelling and monitoring of regional water storage changes, glacier melting, and groundwater depletion, especially when satellite gravity data is integrated.</p>

	<h2>Land Geometry</h2>
Domain	Land
Subdomain	Geometric
Scientific Area	Geometry of land surface with respect to the reference Earth ellipsoid or the geoid and its variations.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Digital Elevation Model (DEM): <i>Geo-located heights of land surface with respect to the reference ellipsoid or the geoid.</i> ▪ Digital Terrain Model (DTM): <i>Heights of terrain of the solid Earth (including bathymetry and bedrock) with respect to the reference ellipsoid or the geoid as geo-located data or spherical harmonic expansion.</i> ▪ Plate Kinematic Model (PKM): <i>Velocity vectors representing the motion of tectonic plates.</i> ▪ Earth Surface Deformation (ESD): <i>Regional models of 3D geometric surface deformation and deformation changes (gradients) over long distances (strain field).</i>

Relevance	<p>Monitoring the land surface and its changes over time is essential for updating and maintaining regional and global reference frames, as they require accurate plate kinematics and deformation models to remain consistent over time. Elevation models are necessary for producing accurate topography maps, contour lines, and elevation profiles, providing the basis for national, regional, and global topographic databases. These databases are essential for orthorectifying satellite images and creating 3D visualizations to extract terrain features and to facilitate land use and land cover classification. They also support river flow modelling and drainage analysis, flood risk assessment and simulation of inundation zones, as well as management of irrigation and water resources. They are also useful for planning radio tower placement, signal coverage, and satellite communications as well as for simulating line-of-sight and interference zones. Terrain models are mandatory to model topography gravity signals in order to improve the accuracy and resolution of the geoid. Horizontal deformation models enable the monitoring of plate tectonics, rift zones, and subduction processes, as well as the detection of fault movements, strain accumulation, and post-seismic deformation. Vertical deformation models are essential for detecting ground subsidence due to groundwater extraction, mining, or oil/gas withdrawal, monitoring uplift from glacial isostatic adjustment, tectonic activity or mountain building, as well as for determining movements induced by glacier melting and permafrost. Vertical land motion estimates in coastal areas are fundamental to measuring relative sea level change for the planning of coastal zone management and climate change adaptation/mitigation.</p>
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	<h2>Sea Surface</h2>
Domain	Ocean
Subdomain	Geometric
Scientific Area	Geometry of ocean surface with respect to the reference Earth ellipsoid.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mean Sea Surface (MSS): <i>Geo-located long-term average sea surface heights.</i> ▪ Sea Level Anomaly (SLA): <i>Time series of geo-located deviations of the instantaneous sea surface from the MSS.</i> ▪ Sea State (SES): <i>Characterization of waves in terms of height.</i> ▪ Empirical Ocean Tide Model (EOT): <i>Sea surface variations due to luni-solar tides.</i>

Relevance	Variations in the sea surface and extreme sea level anomalies are key indicators of climate change. Monitoring the sea surface is essential for studying ocean dynamics, detecting storm surges, tsunamis, or high wave events, and identifying anomalous water levels, which can indicate unusual water temperature or salinity. Time series of sea level anomalies provided by geodesy are important empirical data to improve numerical weather prediction and climate models. Empirical ocean tide models inferred from geodetic observations are essential for removing tidal signals from satellite altimetry data to analyse mean sea level, as they help to distinguish between ocean tidal variability and long-term sea level rise. These models are also essential for predicting tidal contributions to coastal flooding during storms and for safe harbour navigation and marine operations. Furthermore, empirical ocean tide models are necessary to remove the effects of ocean tides from geodetic observations prior to data analysis as well as for precise orbit determination.
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	Sea Level
Domain	Ocean
Subdomain	Physical
Scientific Area	Height of ocean surface with respect to the geoid, which is defined as the global equipotential surface of the Earth's gravity field that is most closely approximated by the global mean sea surface, or with respect to the local equipotential surface at the height reference station of a regional height reference system. The former is known as absolute or global sea level, the latter as relative sea level.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Global Mean Sea Level / Mean Dynamic Topography (MSL/MDT): <i>Geo-located deviation of MSS with respect to the geoid.</i> ▪ Mean Geostrophic Currents (MGC): <i>Geostrophic currents derived from MSL/MDT.</i> ▪ Global Sea Level Change / Dynamic Ocean Topography (SLC/DOT): <i>Time series of geo-located deviations of the instantaneous sea surface height from the geoid.</i> ▪ Relative Mean Sea Level (RMSL): <i>Geo-located deviation of MSS with respect to a local equipotential surface defined by a regional height reference system.</i> ▪ Relative Sea Level Change (RSLC): <i>Time series of geo-located deviations of the instantaneous sea surface height from the</i>

	<i>local equipotential surface defined by a regional height reference system.</i>
Relevance	Sea level is one of the most sensitive and impactful indicators of global climate change. Monitoring changes in the global mean sea level enables to distinguish between ocean mass variations due to melting of glaciers and ice sheets, and ocean volume changes due to thermal expansion. Time series of global sea level observations provided by geodesy are essential for monitoring the global ocean areas, modelling geostrophic currents and seasonal variability, and projecting long-term sea level rise. Relative sea level observations are important for detecting changes in temperature, salinity, and circulation at local levels. These observations combined with vertical land motion data also provided by geodesy are essential for estimating the apparent sea level change in coastal areas, which in turn is needed to inform policy makers in the management of coastal risks.

	Sea Ice
Domain	Ocean
Subdomain	Geometric
Scientific Area	Sea ice coverage in the oceans and ice volume estimation of sea ice.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sea Ice Extension (SIE): <i>Time series of sea ice coverage in the oceans.</i> ▪ Sea Ice Volume (SIV): <i>Volume of sea ice from heights of sea ice above the ocean surface.</i>
Relevance	Sea ice variability is a key indicator of climate change in the polar regions. Observations of sea ice extension and volume provided by geodesy are essential for understanding sea surface variations in the polar regions, monitoring the albedo effect (a main contributor to the Earth's energy budget: less ice means more heat is absorbed by the ocean), and predicting variations in air-sea exchanges of heat, momentum, moisture and gases (essential for assessing the health of marine ecosystems). Geodetic time series of sea ice extension and volume also serve as input data for improving climate and weather models. Geodetic mapping and monitoring of sea ice variations contribute to safe navigation, route planning, and risk reduction from ice hazards.

	<h2>Ice Sheets</h2>
Domain	Land
Subdomain	Geometric/Physical
Scientific Area	Temporal changes of the volume and mass of ice sheets grounded on land surface or seafloor.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ice Mass Change (IMC): <i>Temporal gravity changes from satellite gravimetry missions caused by ice mass change and transport (physical method).</i> ▪ Ice Sheet Thickness (IST): <i>Temporal changes of the thickness of ice sheets from radar and laser altimeters (geometric method). IST is also known as ice grounding line location.</i>
Relevance	<p>Ice sheet variations are sensitive indicators of climate change as their mass balance (gains versus losses) directly indicates global warming. Monitoring ice sheets is essential for understanding how they respond to climate change and projecting how their variations influence the global water cycle, surface energy budget, sea level change, and ocean circulation patterns. Geodesy provides time series of ice volume changes inferred from satellite altimetry measurements, and mass changes inferred from satellite gravimetry. These observations are essential for studying the mass budget (input-output balance), projecting sea level change, improving climate and weather models, predicting changes in ocean salinity and circulation, and informing global climate agreements and adaptation strategies.</p>

	<h2>Glaciers</h2>
Domain	Land
Subdomain	Geometric/Physical
Scientific Area	Temporal changes of the volume and mass of glaciers.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Glacier Mass Change (GMC): <i>Temporal gravity changes from satellite gravimetry missions caused by ice mass change and transport (physical method).</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Glacier Ice Thickness (GIT): <i>Temporal changes of the thickness of glaciers from radar and laser altimeters (geometric method). GIT is also known as glacier elevation change.</i> ▪ Glacier Flow Velocities (GFV): <i>Ice volume changes by glacier flow velocities from interferometric SAR (Synthetic-Aperture Radar) and net snow accumulation from atmospheric models.</i>
Relevance	<p>Changes in glaciers are an indicator of climate change as their mass balance (gains versus losses) directly reflects global warming. Glacier changes over time impact the global sea level and the regional water cycle and may increase local hazard risks. Geodesy provides time series data of ice volume changes inferred from satellite altimetry observations, flow velocities inferred from interferometric SAR, and mass changes inferred from satellite gravimetry (although limited to large glaciers). This information is essential for studying mass balance, identifying contributors to sea level change, monitoring availability of fresh water, predicting/mitigating risks associated with ice melting, and informing regional and global climate agreements and adaptation strategies.</p>

	<h2>Inland Water Level</h2>
Domain	Land
Subdomain	Geometric/Physical
Scientific Area	Water levels of inland lakes and rivers for estimating water mass variations and water runoff into the oceans.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mean Regional Water Level (MRWL): <i>Mean water level of inland lakes and rivers.</i> ▪ Regional Water Level Change (RWLC): <i>Time series of water levels of inland lakes and rivers.</i>
Relevance	<p>Monitoring inland water levels (in lakes, rivers, reservoirs, and wetlands) is essential for environmental sustainability, disaster preparedness, and resource management. Geodesy provides time series of inland water levels from satellite altimetry and optical remote sensing imagery that combined with in-situ measurements improve hydrological models. These models are the basis to understand the impact of climate change on the hydrological cycle, to plan freshwater consumption and recharge, to manage dams and hydropower plants, to forecast risks associated with floods or droughts, and to inform local and regional policies on water management and environmental conservation.</p>

Terrestrial Water Storage

Domain	Land
Subdomain	Physical
Scientific Area	Total amount of water stored in all continental storage compartments (ice caps, glaciers, snow cover, soil moisture, groundwater, surface water bodies, water in biomass). The change of Terrestrial Water Storage (TWS) over time balances the budget of the water fluxes precipitation, evapotranspiration, and runoff; i.e., it closes the continental water balance.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Terrestrial Water Storage Anomaly (TWSA): <i>Calculated from a time series of global gravity field models relative to the long-term mean in terms of equivalent water heights.</i>
Relevance	Monitoring TWS is essential for understanding the global water cycle, managing water resources, and assessing climate change impacts. Declines in TWS reveal emerging drought conditions. Excessive changes in TWS can indicate flood risk due to soil saturation or snowpack melt. Geodetic satellite gravity missions are able to detect mass changes associated with large-scale water movement on or near the Earth's surface. The time series of Earth's gravity field changes provided by geodesy are essential for monitoring anomalies in terrestrial water storage related to major flood and drought events at global to regional scales, which in turn are fundamental data for quantifying the global hydrological water cycle. The ability to directly monitor global mass redistribution has proven the essential contribution of geodesy to validating and constraining climate models, supporting climate adaptation strategies, and informing regional and global climate agreements.

Atmosphere Parameters

Domain	Global
Subdomain	Physical
Scientific Area	Determination of the non-hydrostatic refractive effect of the lower atmosphere on radio signals. Electron content of the ionosphere for

	considering delays of radio waves. Assimilation of geodetic observations to physically driven thermosphere density models.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrated Water Vapor (IWV): <i>Neutral atmosphere zenith and slant wet delays as well as gradients describing the integrated water vapor content.</i> ▪ Global Ionosphere Maps (GIM): <i>Global maps of the vertical total electron content.</i> ▪ Thermosphere Density Model (TDM): <i>Time and space dependent scale factors determined from geodetic data for physical thermosphere density models.</i>
Relevance	Space geodetic observations based on microwaves experience propagation distortions (delays and bending) due to atmospheric conditions. The analysis of these distortions is essential to remove their effects from geodetic observations prior to data processing. In turn, the detected distortions provide valuable information about atmospheric properties such as water vapor content in the troposphere and electron content in the ionosphere. In combination with solar observations, geodesy also contributes to our understanding of the interactions between the magnetosphere, ionosphere, plasmasphere and thermosphere. Atmospheric products provided by geodesy are essential for improving weather forecasting models, studying climate change and its impact on the atmosphere, and predicting space weather events that can affect satellites, navigation, communication and power systems, or space mission launches and returns.

3.2 Level 2 EGVs

	<h2>Satellite Orbits</h2>
Domain	Global
Subdomain	Geometric
Scientific Area	GNSS satellite orbits provide the basis for precise positioning on ground, for precise orbit determination of satellites and for navigation and timing applications. They are essential for Earth system studies. Together with precise satellite clocks and biases, they allow for a precise point positioning (PPP) for single stations with a precision on the several millimetre level in the agreed terrestrial reference frame (TRF). Code biases are required for code-based GNSS positioning and for extracting the total electron content (TEC) of the ionosphere, among other applications. Additional phase biases are a prerequisite

	for precise point positioning with ambiguity resolution (PPP-AR). Precise orbits of Earth Observation satellites are needed for optimally exploiting their instrument data and for reliable Earth Observation products. Consistently recomputed precise orbit information is essential for geodetic products.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ GNSS Satellite Orbits, Clocks and Biases (GOCB) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Orbits: <i>Ephemerides of GNSS satellites.</i> - Clocks: <i>Clock solution for GNSS satellites.</i> - Code and phase biases: <i>Solutions for systematic errors between GNSS observations at the same or different frequencies.</i> ▪ Earth Observation Satellite Orbits (ESO): <i>Orbits and attitude data of Earth Observation satellites.</i>
Relevance	Precise satellite orbits (including GNSS satellite clock corrections and signal biases) are essential for reliable satellite-based services, such as positioning, navigation, timing, Earth Observation, remote sensing, etc. Errors in satellite information can lead to disruptions in everyday applications (inaccurate positioning, failed navigation, timing issues, etc.) and misrepresentation of Earth Observation results (sea level monitoring, terrestrial water storage, ice coverage surveillant, etc.). GNSS code and/or phase biases are essential for high-precision positioning applications like PPP-AR, as well as non-navigation applications such as ionospheric analysis and time transfer. Highly precise (and long-term stable) orbits for altimetry satellites are essential to ensure a reliable monitoring of sea level variations over decades, which is of great societal relevance for policy makers to protect people in coastal regions.

	<h2>Station Positions and Variations</h2>
Domain	Global
Subdomain	Geometric
Scientific Area	3D station positions (referred to a reference epoch), constant velocities, seasonal variations and discontinuities of points observed by space geodetic techniques (completed by acoustic ranging seafloor stations in ocean areas).
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Station Position Time Series (SPTS): <i>Product contains lists of stations, plots of position coordinates, seasonal signals, non-tidal loading series, discontinuity data (e.g., earthquakes and</i>

	<i>instrument changes), station velocities, atmospheric integrated water vapor, quality assessment statistics, tables of data holdings.</i>
Relevance	Geodetic space techniques allow us to determine station positions with high accuracy (at the mm level). Continuous operating stations measure large- and small-scale displacements with high spatial and temporal resolutions. Geodetic techniques (especially GNSS) are widely applied for deformation monitoring of natural hazards (volcano activity, seismic effects, landslides, subsidence, etc.), man-made structures (dams, buildings, bridges, mines, etc.), and also modelling tectonic features (plate motion, surface deformation, slow-slip interactions, etc.) including vertical movements associated to mountain building or global isostatic adjustment. Recent improvements in the observing technologies, data analysis strategies, and standards have increased sensitivity and accuracy of the geodetic results, and today it is even possible to detect small (transient) signals of surface deformation caused by e.g. oceanic, hydrologic, or atmospheric loading. Time series of station positions provided by geodesy are essential for studying Earth's surface deformation, geodynamics, and geophysical phenomena as well as for monitoring and understanding various environmental changes, such as ice and snow coverage variations and sea-level changes.

	Sea Water Level Records
Domain	Ocean
Subdomain	Geometric
Scientific Area	Height of the sea water level with respect to a local height reference recorded by a water level recorder (tide gauge).
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sea Water Level Records (SWLR): <i>Data per recording station: Monthly and annual local mean sea level values; local mean sea level trends; local mean sea level anomalies; sea level reconstructions (prediction of historical data).</i>
Relevance	Sea water levels measured by tide gauges represent relative changes as they reflect the superposition of absolute water level changes and local or regional land vertical movements affecting the mareographs. To obtain absolute sea level changes from tide gauge records, they have to be corrected by vertical land motion (see product ESD). The vertical land motion is usually determined by repeated or continuous GNSS positioning. Averaging tide gauge records over long time periods eliminates most time dependent variations. The time series analysis

	of tide gauge records provides insights into climate change effects, decadal climate variability, tides, storm surges, meltwater inflow, tsunamis, and other coastal processes. These data are also essential for detecting errors or drifts in satellite altimetry and to validate ocean models. In tectonically active areas (like island arcs), historical tide gauge records are regarded as a source of information on long-term secular vertical movements (and sometimes co-seismic uplifts) useful for studying crustal movements during periods before space geodesy. Historical tide gauge records are also essential for reliable sea level reconstructions.
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	<h2>Land and Marine Gravity Data</h2>
Domain	Land/Ocean
Subdomain	Physical
Scientific Area	Gravity data acquired at the Earth’s surface or by airborne campaigns with different types of instruments (absolute, relative) on land or at the oceans as observation per epoch or as observation time series.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Land Gravity Data (LGD): <i>Surface or airborne gravity data per country or per campaign over land or inland waters from relative gravimetry.</i> ▪ Marine Gravity Data (MGD): <i>Gravity data over the oceans by ship or airborne gravimetry from relative gravimetry.</i> ▪ Absolute Gravity Data (AGD): <i>Gravity data observed with absolute gravimetry instruments.</i> ▪ Time Series Gravity Data (TGD): <i>Gravity data at stations with continuously operating superconducting gravimeters or repeated absolute gravity measurements.</i>
Relevance	<p>Ground, airborne and marine gravity data are essential for increasing the resolution and accuracy of satellite gravity data as they capture small-scale gravity features not visible (or attenuated) to the satellite gravity missions. Well-distributed terrestrial gravity data is essential for the determination of the geoid and, consequently, for the establishment and maintenance of physical height reference systems. Time and space-dependent changes of gravity yield information on the distribution and movement of Earth’s masses. Time series of gravity data are essential for modelling and monitoring geodynamic and geophysical processes. Satellite gravimetry provides a unique, global, and homogeneous data set of mass anomalies within or on the surface of the Earth. However, current satellite gravimetry is unable to resolve structures smaller than a few hundred kilometres.</p>

	<p>To increase the spatio-temporal resolution of satellite gravimetry and to be able to detect short-term and small-scale mass changes, terrestrial gravimetry is essential. Terrestrial gravimeters can detect changes in mass distribution within a radius of a few hundred meters from the instrument. Thus, terrestrial gravimetry is an important tool to monitor low-frequency seismicity, volcanic systems, geothermal reservoirs, effects of irrigation or water withdrawal, impacts of large building projects, etc. Terrestrial gravity data is also essential for geophysical prospection, and it is widely used in the exploration of natural resources like oil and gas, as well as in mining and in geotechnical, archaeological, metrological and geomatics studies.</p>
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3.3 Level 1 EGVs

	<h2>Geodetic Observations</h2>
Domain	Global
Subdomain	Geometric/Physical
Scientific Area	Specific measurements and data collected using various techniques to determine the Earth's shape, gravity field and orientation as functions of space and time.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geodetic Geometric Observations (GGO) such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Microwave observations of extragalactic objects (quasars) by VLBI,</i> - <i>Laser ranging to LEO satellites, GNSS satellites, and to the Moon,</i> - <i>Microwave observations from GNSS satellites at the ground and at LEO satellites,</i> - <i>Microwave observations from ground stations to LEO satellites (DORIS),</i> - <i>Radar and optical observations of the Earth's surface (land, ice, glaciers, ocean, etc.) from remote sensing satellites,</i> - <i>Distance measurements between satellites (K-band, laser interferometry, optical methods, etc.),</i> - <i>Tide gauge measurements,</i> - <i>GNSS reflectometry and GNSS radio occultation.</i> ▪ Geodetic Physical Observations (GPO) such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Measurement of acceleration and gravity gradients with sensors on board LEO satellites,</i> - <i>Absolute and relative gravity measurements with sensors on or near the ground,</i>

	- <i>Optical atomic clock comparisons to measure gravity potential differences.</i>
Relevance	Geodetic observations are essential for procuring and maintaining the essential geodetic variables. Without these observations, there would be no data, geodetic products, or research results to support these variables. Observations from space geodetic techniques are essential for providing accurate and long-term stable global reference frames and for observing and understanding Earth dynamics. Each space geodetic technique is sensitive to different Earth signals, conducts observations with different resolutions in space and time, and provides geodetic products with different latency and quality. Satellites at high altitudes (MEO and GEO) are preferred for positioning, as they are less influenced by gravitational and air drag perturbations. Geodetic LEO satellites are preferred for determining the Earth’s gravity field (as they are more sensitive to short-wavelength gravity components) and for mapping the Earth’s surface (topography, oceans, ice caps, lakes, rivers, and soil moisture). Satellites have the big advantage that they collect data homogeneously and consistently over large parts of the Earth’s surface. They also allow the collection of data that cannot be recorded at the Earth’s surface. Observations based on LEO satellites are essential to monitor sea level, ice sheets, water storage on land, atmospheric water content, high-resolution surface motion and variation in the Earth’s gravity field. Observations from terrestrial techniques are essential for increasing spatial and temporal resolutions of satellite-based observations, for validating satellite-based data, and for detecting short-scale or high-frequency signals of the Earth system that are invisible for satellites.

3.4 Basis EGVs

	Geodetic Standards and Conventions
Domain	Global
Subdomain	Geometric/Physical
Scientific Area	Geodetic numerical standards and conventions are essential for ensuring the consistency and accuracy of geodetic data analysis and product generation. These standards address various aspects, such as physical units, constants, and background models for corrections and reductions.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Numerical Standards in Geodesy (NSG), <i>such as speed of light, geocentric gravitational constant, reference-level ellipsoid,</i>

	<p><i>potential value of the geoid, geometric-size parameters of the Earth (e.g., equatorial radius and flattening factor), dynamical form factor of the Earth, mean equatorial gravity, atomic time scales, transformation between permanent-tide concepts; etc.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Conventional Background Models (CBM) are a priori models used for data processing. They are regarded as known and are expected to be at least as accurate as the geodetic observation data. Examples include corrections for phase centre variations in emitting and receiving antennas, tidal corrections for the solid Earth tide, permanent tide, and solid Earth pole tide, ocean and atmospheric tide loading effects, a priori tropospheric zenith delays, etc.</i>
Relevance	<p>Geodetic standards and conventions are essential for consistent data analysis and for achieving accuracy, reliability, and interoperability of geodetic results. Different geodetic techniques observe the same Earth, but detect different signals, with different spatial and temporal resolutions, sensitivities and latencies. To ensure that any changes detected after analysis of geodetic data truly represent changes in the Earth system and not inconsistencies in data preparation and analysis, the same standards and conventions must be used across the various geodetic techniques. Unified and consistent standards and conventions are thus essential for the generation of high-quality geodetic products, data integration and interoperability as well as modelling and correct interpretation of results.</p>

	<h2>Geodetic Infrastructure</h2>
Domain	Global
Subdomain	Geometric/Physical
Scientific Area	Geodetic infrastructure refers to the systems and technologies used to accurately measure and depict the Earth's shape, orientation, and gravity field, as well as the changes that occur over time.
EGV Stewards	tbd
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Geodetic Space Infrastructure (GSI) comprises the space segment of space geodetic techniques such as quasars for VLBI and satellites for SLR, DORIS, GNSS, gravity field missions, radar and optical satellite altimetry, radar interferometry, radar occultation, etc.</i> ▪ <i>Geodetic Terrestrial Infrastructure (GTI) comprises the ground segments of space geodetic infrastructure (such as station networks and operational centres for data collection, analysis and distribution) as well as the sensors/instruments of</i>

	<i>terrestrial techniques such as tide gauges, absolute and relative gravity meters (including superconducting and quantum gravity meters), GNSS reflectometry, optical atomic clocks, and geometric angle, distance and levelling methods.</i>
Relevance	The geodetic infrastructure comprises not only the observing instruments but also data management, data analysis, data distribution, and research. The observing infrastructure consists of a variety of techniques using sensors and instruments on the ground (land and sea), in the air and in space that collect data essential for monitoring the shape, gravity field and orientation of the Earth. Space geodetic techniques provide comprehensive observations at global and regional scales, while terrestrial techniques are needed to increase the spatial and temporal resolution of measurements, to calibrate and validate the space techniques, and to capture specific local features. The data infrastructure includes facilities for data transfer, data management and archiving, and data and product dissemination. An important role within the data infrastructure is the quality assessment and control of data, as well as the alignment to international standards ensuring interoperability, efficiency of data processing, and decision-making. The analysis infrastructure covers the complete and consistent data processing chain from the initial acquisition and the analysis of large volumes of observations to the consistent integrated analysis and combination of technique-specific products. The research infrastructure comprises the resources, facilities, and services needed to advance scientific knowledge, drive innovation, and address complex science challenges. It is crucial for cutting-edge research and development to keep pace with technological advances in measurement techniques and the assimilation of observations into complex models of the Earth system and its components.

3.5 Overview EGVs and Geodetic Products

Table 3 provides an overview about the geodetic products contributing to the EGVs:

- **Red** indicates the primary geodetic products directly related to the EGV;
- **Blue** indicates the geodetic products that provide important information to the EGV;
- **Orange** indicates geodetic products indirectly linked to the EGV.

Table 3: Overview of geodetic products contributing to the EGVs

Geodetic Products	Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs)																					
	L3 EGVs											L2 EGVs		L1	Basis							
	Earth Orientation Parameters	Global Reference Frames	Global Earth Gravity Field	Regional Reference Frames	Regional Gravity Field Model	Land Geometry	Sea Surface	Sea Level	Sea Ice	Ice Sheets	Glaciers	Inland Water Level	Terrestrial Water Storage	Atmosphere Parameters	Satellite Orbits	Station Positions and Variations	Sea Water Level Records	Land and Marine Gravity Data	Geodetic Observations	Standards and Conventions	Infrastructure	
AGD: Absolute Gravity Data																						
CBM: Conventional Background Models																						
CPO: Celestial Pole Offset																						
CRF: Celestial Reference Frame																						
DEM: Digital Elevation Model																						
DOT: Dynamic Ocean Topography																						
DTM: Digital Terrain Model																						
EOT: Empirical Ocean Tide Model																						
ESD: Earth Surface Deformation																						
ESO: Earth Observation Satellite Orbits																						
GFQ: Gravity Field Quantities																						
GFV: Glacier Flow Velocities																						
GGM: Global Gravity Field Models																						
GGO: Geodetic Geometric Observations																						
GIM: Global Ionosphere Maps																						
GIT: Glacier Ice Thickness																						
GMC: Glacier Mass Change																						
GOCB: GNSS Satellite Orbits, Clocks, Biases																						
GPO: Geodetic Physical Observations																						
GRF: Gravity Reference Frame																						
GSI: Geodetic Space Infrastructure																						
GTI: Geodetic Terrestrial Infrastructure																						
HRF: Height Reference Frame																						
IMC: Ice Mass Change																						
IST: Ice Sheet Thickness																						
IWV: Integrated Water Vapor																						
LGD: Land Gravity Data																						
LOD: Length of Day																						
MDT: Mean Dynamic Topography																						
MGC: Mean Geostrophic Currents																						
MGD: Marine Gravity Data																						
MRWL: Mean Regional Water Level																						
MSL: (Global) Mean Sea Level																						
MSS: Mean Sea Surface																						
NSG: Numerical Standards in Geodesy																						
PKM: Plate Kinematic Model																						
PM: Polar Motion																						
RGFQ: Regional Gravity Field Quantities																						
RGM: Regional Geoid Model																						
RGRF: Regional Gravity Reference Frame																						
RHRF: Regional Height Reference Frame																						
RMSL: Relative Mean Sea Level																						
RSLC: Relative Sea Level Change																						
RTRF: Regional Terrestrial Reference Frame																						
RWLC: Regional Water Level Change																						
SES: Sea State																						
SIE: Sea Ice Extension																						
SIV: Sea Ice Volume																						
SLA: Sea Level Anomaly																						
SLC: (Global) Sea Level Change																						
SPTS: Station Position Time Series																						
SWLR: Sea Water Level Records																						
TDM: Thermosphere Density Model																						
TGD: Time Series Gravity Data																						
TGFM: Topographic Gravity Field Model																						
TRF: Terrestrial Reference Frame																						
TWSA: Terrestrial Water Storage Anomaly																						
UT1: Universal Time																						
VDP: Vertical Datum Parameter																						

■ Geodetic products directly related to the EGV
■ Geodetic products that provide important information to the EGV
■ Geodetic products indirectly linked to the EGV

The Way Forward

This document presents the first catalogue of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs). This concept was developed within the framework of GGOS and refined through comments and revisions from numerous colleagues. The EGV classification and associated products are primarily based on those products currently generated within the IAG and have been extended to include products developed outside the IAG, for example by space and national agencies, research institutes, universities, etc. The overarching goal is to raise awareness of the essential role of geodesy in monitoring the Earth system. This catalogue is not static, it is a living document that will evolve with technological and methodological advances and be updated as new products emerge, or existing products improve in accuracy, resolution, or latency.

The process of defining, adopting and maintaining the EGVs demands a coordinated framework across global, regional and national geodetic stakeholders. Progress depends on enhanced data interoperability, standardized processing methodologies and sustained international collaboration to ensure the continuity, comparability and reliability of geodetic data. This catalogue marks the beginning of this long-term process. The next steps include:

- **Characterization of products supporting the EGVs:** Each geodetic product must be systematically described and evaluated in terms of purpose, performance, quality, availability, uncertainty, spatial and temporal resolution, timeliness, and data sources. Clear documentation of methodologies, conventions, and limitations is essential to facilitate use by non-geodetic communities. Access to EGVs and related geodetic products should be provided through the GGOS Portal, which offers detailed metadata while datasets and research results remain physically located in their original data centres.
- **Identification of stewards for the EGVs:** A main requirement of the EGVs is that they are sustainable. They should be provided on a long-term basis, and their reliability and consistency should be ensured.

In this context, stewards must be identified who will take responsibility for safeguarding the long-term integrity, functionality, and adaptability of the EGVs. These stewards should act on behalf of broader stakeholders to ensure responsible management, transparency, and continuous improvement. Identifying and engaging these stewards is a key next step.

- **Periodic reviews to reassess relevance, priorities, and emerging needs:** Mechanisms must be established to evaluate, update or rationalize the EGVs and associated products according to improved geodetic observations, methods and results. This process requires continuous feedback from IAG Components, external operational agencies and data providers, geodetic and non-geodetic users as well as research groups in geodesy.

Through GGOS, the IAG provides a common framework to encourage, coordinate and facilitate Earth-monitoring efforts by integrating observations collected by different national and international organizations. This approach is similar to that taken by GCOS and GOOS. From the outset, these observing systems were designed to serve as clearinghouse for expertise and as central interface between science and society. They do not own instruments, run stations or produce data themselves. Instead, they rely on contributions from countries and organizations working on climate and ocean research and protection to maintain the ECVs and EOVs. In this context, the IAG and GGOS call on everyone involved in geodesy to support the monitoring, sustainability and further development of the EGVs. The IAG and GGOS encourage and appreciate contributions from anyone who wishes to support this effort.

